

The Thermal Decomposition of Barium Nitrite

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Amongst the nitrites of the alkaline earth group metals a characteristic feature of the thermal decomposition of barium nitrite is its production of comparatively large amounts of nitrogen. No satisfactory explanation of this has been found for this. The present work shows that the reactivity of barium oxide to nitric oxide forming barium nitrite and nitrogen is a conspicuous feature of the decomposition: this might happen through the intermediate production and consumption of barium peroxide. The formation, decomposition and reformation of nitrate and nitrite is a feature of the decomposition of alkali and alkaline earth nitrites. In the case of barium nitrite, the formation of barium oxide, nitric oxide and nitrogen dioxide is observed and all these are found to play a very active role in the formation of nitrogen. Most of the reactions appear to occur only in the solid phase though the reaction occurring at the gas-solid interface are neither absent nor insignificant. Results of the action of nitric oxide on barium nitrite, barium nitrate and barium oxide are also reported.

Barium nitrite¹ and calcium nitrite² decompose in the identical ranges of temperatures, 380°-400°, still producing different amounts of nitrogen. Strontium nitrite decomposes above 500°³. The latter reacts with nitric oxide at 300° but barium nitrite is found not to do so up to 350° and seems to produce nitrogen by a different mechanism involving the action of nitric oxide on barium oxide⁴⁻⁵.

Ray and Ganguli¹ studied the decomposition of alkaline earth nitrites and observed that the barium and strontium salts produced more nitrogen while the calcium and magnesium salts produced less. Oswald⁶ studied the behaviour of nitrites and of the oxides of nitrogen to heat in some detail. Ray and Ganguli seem to be of the view that the nitrate¹ oxide, nitric oxide and nitrogen were all formed simultaneously in the primary stage of the decomposition but Oswald was of the view that the primary stage consisted of the dissociation as (1) $M(NO_3)_2 \rightleftharpoons MO + NO + NO_2$. Oza and his co-workers⁷ held the same view for the primary stage of the decomposition but were not in agreement with Oswald in the mode of formation of nitrogen as (2) $M(NO_3)_2 + NO_2 \rightarrow M(NO_2)_2 + \frac{1}{2}N_2$. In the case of sodium⁸ and strontium⁵ nitrites, nitrogen was shown formed as (3) $M(NO_3)_2 + 2NO \rightarrow M(NO_2)_2 + N_2$ and that the shortage of nitrogen in the case of the calcium salt was shown to be due to the operation of the equilibrium (4) $M(NO_3)_2 + 2NO \rightleftharpoons M(NO_2)_2 + 2NO_2$.

A careful examination of the products of decomposition under different conditions shows that the initial dissociations (1) is followed by reactions in close chain forming

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7. T. M. Oza and M. S. Shah, *J. Univ. Bom.*, 1942, XI (3), 70.
8. T. M. Oza, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 173; T. M. Oza and B. R. Walawalker, *ibid.*, 243.

nitrate and reforming nitrite and nitrogen; that when the proportion of nitrate in the system approaches 25% nitrogen production suffers hindrance. Experiments show also that nitric oxide acts vigorously on barium oxide at about 300° producing nitrogen and the action is likely to be very vigorous at the temperature at which barium nitrite decomposes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: Barium nitrite monohydrate was prepared as in Oza and Dipali⁹ and dehydrated over P_2O_5 in vacuum. Found: Ba, 59.85, $\cdot NO_2$, 40.1%. $Ba(NO_2)_2$ requires, Ba, 59.88, NO_2 , 40.13%. Barium nitrate was BDH. (A.R.). Found: Ba, 52.6, NO_3 , 47.3; $Ba(NO_3)_2$ requires Ba, 52.55, NO_3 , 47.45%. Barium Oxide, was Merck's (extra pure) ignited; Found Ba, 89.88, BaO requiring 89.56%. Pure nitric oxide was prepared by heating silver nitrite. The apparatus was essentially the same as in Oza and Oza³ and Oza, Thaker and Oza¹⁰ (Fig. 1). Analyses were done as in Oza and Oza³ barium being determined with K_2SO_4 or H_2SO_4 using sodium rhodizonate as indicator.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table I shows results of experiments on the effect of temperature (1-4), of mass (5-8), of time (9-14) and of the addition of barium nitrate (18-20) on the decomposition of barium nitrite. The decomposition is slow at 400° about 6.0 ml. gas being formed by 0.250 g sub. in 1 hr. The solid products (exp. 1) show the lowest value for barium nitrate, ratio $BaO/Ba(NO_2)_2$, being the highest here in all the 14 expts. This would indicate that oxide, not nitrate, is formed in the primary stage of the decomposition. Nitric oxide is the major gaseous product (80-70%) while the proportions of nitrogen dioxide and nitrogen are high at 400° when the reactions are slow; the latter diminishes at higher temperatures but nitrogen dioxide increases again at 550° when the system is depleted with nitrite. Increase of mass (exps. 6-8) depresses $BaO/Ba(NO_2)_2$ ratio, increases the proportion of nitrogen appreciably and retards the production of nitrogen dioxide and nitric oxide showing that the latter are more efficiently consumed in the solid phase. The consumption of barium nitrite does not increase in proportion to mass and so does production of barium oxide. The production of barium nitrate keeps pace well with mass a little more of it being produced than required by the mass of nitrite taken. The production of more nitrate and nitrogen would favour Eq. (3) but nitrite is not consumed in that proportion which shows that it is being replenished and as net barium oxide production is also less, the view that barium nitrite is produced in the reaction which consumes barium oxide finds favour. The production of nitrate and consumption of oxides of nitrogen with increased mass indicate that the reactions occur in the solid phase. At 520° (Exps. 9-14) the reaction rate is very high about 80 per cent of the total nitrite consumed in 120 mts. being used up in the first 5 mts. only. Value of the ratio $BaO/Ba(NO_2)_2$ is the smallest at 5 mts. showing that more nitrate is produced in the first 5 mts. than thereafter. With lapse of time barium oxide increases faster than barium nitrate but nitrogen-producing reaction is repressed after the initial 5 mts. as the nitrate content of the system gets high. Absence of large proportions of nitrogen in these high

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10. T. M. Oza, V. T. Oza and R. H. Thaker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2457.

temperature experiments shows that the reaction (5) $\text{BaO} + 3\text{NO} \rightarrow \text{Ba}(\text{NO}_2)_2 + \frac{1}{2}\text{N}_2$ (see later) is perhaps more of a solid phase reaction than an interface one.

TABLE I

The effect of temperature, mass, time and of addition of barium nitrite on the decomposition of barium nitrite

Exps. 1 to 4: temp. varied, time 1 hr., mass 0.250g; 5 to 8: mass varied, time 1 hr., temp. 450°C; 9 to 14: time varied, temp. 520°C, mass 0.025 g. 15 to 20: with added barium nitrate, time 1 hr., temp. 475°C.

Exp. No.	Variable factor Temp. °C	Solid Products (g. mole $\times 10^{-4}$)		Ratio: BaO/ Ba (NO ₂) ₂ (g. mole).	Ba (NO ₂) ₂ consumed (g. mole $\times 10^{-4}$).	Gaseous Products (N.T.P.)				
		Ba (NO ₃) ₂	BaO			Total	NO%	NO ₂ ml N ₂	NO ₂ ml N ₂	
1	400	0.74	1.7	2.3	2.5	6.3	60.3	17.5	22.2	
2	430	1.41	2.3	1.6	3.7	13.8	65.8	15.0	19.2	
3	450	1.68	3.0	1.8	4.7	11.5	69.6	13.0	17.4	
4	550	3.27	6.4	2.0	9.8	25.7	69.4	24.1	12.5	
Mass: g.										
5	0.250	1.63	3.0	1.9	4.7	11.5	75.8	13.0	17.4	
6	0.500	3.20	4.5	1.4	7.9	15.5	61.3	7.1	31.6	
7	0.750	5.30	5.5	1.0	11.0	18.6	60.0	6.2	33.8	
8	1.000	7.20	7.7	1.0	14.9	25.0	57.1	4.7	38.1	
Time: mt:										
9	5	2.3	3.2	1.4	5.6	13.0	67.5	13.0	14.6	
10	15	2.4	4.2	1.7	6.6	15.5	70.3	9.7	20.0	
11	30	2.5	4.5	1.8	7.2	16.9	68.1	11.2	20.7	
12	45	3.0	4.9	1.6	8.0	18.8	69.1	12.2	18.6	
13	9.0	3.4	5.5	1.6	8.9	20.2	71.8	10.9	17.2	
14	120	3.6	5.8	1.6	9.5	22.9	68.6	16.6	14.8	
Mixtures: g.										
Ba (NO ₂) ₂ —Ba (NO ₃) ₂										
15	0.250+0.00	2.3	3.2	1.4	5.7	11.4	70.0	7.9	22.0	
16	0.237+0.0125	2.1	3.3	1.6	5.6	12.8	74.3	11.7	14.1	
17	0.225+0.0250	1.9	3.0	1.6	5.3	11.1	73.0	9.9	18.0	
18	0.1879+0.0625	1.5	2.7	1.8	4.4	11.6	79.3	13.8	7.3	
19	0.125+0.125	0.7	1.7	2.4	2.5	7.9	76.7	15.7	7.8	
20	0.0625+0.1875	0.23	0.7	3.0	1.0	3.1	74.9	22.8	3.0	

That the presence of nitrate in the decomposing nitrite in amounts greater than a certain minimum retards or inhibits the production of nitrogen is well brought out by expts. 18-20. The proportion of nitric oxide is the highest in these experiments. The absence of large proportions of nitrogen dioxide and the presence of large proportions of nitric oxide and poor proportions of nitrogen in these experiments favour the view that nitrogen dioxide is reduced in contact with nitrite to nitric oxide but not to nitrogen (*cf Oswald*).

Experiments done to measure the extent of interface reaction of nitric oxide with barium nitrate, nitrite and oxide showed that up to 350° nitric oxide had little action on

barium nitrite but with barium nitrate nitrogen dioxide was formed at 375° while with barium oxide nitrogen and nitrite were formed as early as 200° in 1 hr. by nitric oxide at 10.0 cm. Hg pressure. Results of the action of nitric oxide atmosphere at 8.0 cm. Hg pressure on 0.250 g. barium nitrate for different periods of time at 500° are given in Table II. These show that (a) barium oxide is not formed in 2 hrs. at 500° although the nitrite is present showing operation of equilibrium (eq. 4); (b) although barium oxide is formed thereafter in 3 and 5 hrs. no nitrogen is formed—evidently as the system is rich in nitrate content, and (c) barium nitrite accumulates up to a limit, in the system containing barium oxide, nitric oxide and nitrogen dioxide, the products of its dissociation, an observation which favours the view of dissociation (Oswald) at the onset of the decomposition. The results of the action of nitric oxide at 5, 10, 15 cm Hg pressure on 0.250 g. barium oxide at 300° for 1 hr., given in Table III, show that the action is very pronounced up to nitric oxide pressure of 10 cm. Hg. some considerable nitrite and nitrogen being formed. Higher nitric oxide pressures had no corresponding great effect presumably because once the surface of barium oxide got covered with barium nitrite no further reaction could occur. Table III shows that the main reaction producing nitrogen in the decomposition of barium nitrite is, in all probability, the overall reaction (5) $\text{BaO} + 3\text{NO} \rightarrow \text{Ba}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2 + \frac{1}{2}\text{N}_2$ proceeding through the intermediate formation and reaction of barium peroxide^{4,5}. The reason why calcium nitrite does not produce large amounts of nitrogen in its decomposition lies in the relatively more covalent character of calcium oxide as compared with barium oxide which (latter) being largely ionic forms a more stable peroxide. The mechanism of formation of this peroxide is explained where⁶ it is also shown that calcium oxide does not produce large amounts of nitrite and nitrogen in contact with nitric oxide.

TABLE II

Effect of Nitric Oxide Atmosphere at 8.0 cm. Hg Pressure on 0.250 g Barium nitrate at 500°C.

Period heating hr. of	NO ₂ formed, ml.	Barium Nitrite formed, g × 10 ⁻⁴	Barium Oxide formed g × 10 ⁻⁴
1	1.25	49.32	Nil
2	1.31	53.32	Nil
3	4.42	56.20	59.2
5	5.88	28.60	97.3

TABLE III

Effect of Nitric Oxide at 5, 10, 15 cm. Hg Pressure on 0.250 g Barium Oxide at 300°C for 1 hr.

NO Pressure	N ₂ formed, ml.	Ba (NO ₂) ₂ formed: g.
5	2.5	0.0293
10	7.0	0.1214
15	8.7	0.1285

CONCLUSION

The above observations along with those on the action of dinitrogen tetroxide on barium nitrite and barium oxide¹² enable an insight into the reactions that occur in the

decomposition of barium nitrite. The start of the decomposition as (1) is followed, close at hand, by reactions consuming more barium nitrite so that initially the consumption of barium nitrite is great. Barium nitrate is formed by the action of nitrogen dioxide on nitrite enriching the system with nitric oxide as (6) $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_2)_2 + 2\text{NO}_2 \rightarrow \text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + 2\text{NO}$. and by the action of nitric oxide on barium oxide as (5) producing nitrogen and nitrite (—a part of which passes into nitrate at the prevailing high temperature). Some barium oxide will react with nitrogen dioxide also, which at the temperature of the decomposition (above 400°), will form much more nitrate than nitrite, this reaction also generating nitric oxide in proportion to the amount of nitrate formed¹². The action of nitric oxide on barium oxide is likely to be vigorous at the temperature of decomposition of the nitrite, since at the instant of formation it will be in intimate contact with barium oxide in the solid mass. This explains the appearance of large amounts of nitrate and nitrogen in the products formed at the start of the decomposition. Barium oxide and barium nitrate, the products, are then under an atmosphere consisting largely of nitric oxide so that interface reactions (4) and (5), producing nitrite, nitrogen dioxide and nitrogen come into being. The nitrate present will hinder the production of nitrogen as soon as its quantity reaches an optimum—explaining fall in nitrogen production after the start. Both (4) and (5) and, to a certain extent, also the action of nitrogen dioxide on barium oxide, regenerate nitrite in the system. Thus a closely interdependent set of reactions ensue reproducing and re-consuming nitrate and nitrite producing, in the ultimate sequence, the products found at the end of the decomposition along with some nitrite (eq. 4) since nitrate and nitric oxide are among the end products. Ardat had noted¹¹ that "even after prolonged ignition its (barium nitrite's) decomposition is not complete".

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12. Action of Dinitrogen Tetroside on Barium Nitrite and Barium Oxide (Paper under publication).